

Relation between the geometric shape of the earth and the number of days in the lunar year

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Abstract :

By studying the geometric shape of the earth which scientists have proven to have a flat surface at the north pole and south pole and vertigo at the equator, I guess there was a relationship between the geometric shape of a circumference of the earth and the number of days in the lunar year.

As we know the geometric shape of the earth was a source of research for several scholars in previous centuries. Most of them realized that it is spherical, then they discovered that the north and south poles are thus flattened with an equatorial vertigo.

According to these important results and which are or which present the starting points of my research of which I think that there was a fundamental relation between the secret geometric form of the earth as well as the measures and the angles adopted in its creation and the number of days in the lunar year.

Also, I will unveil the secret or where did the ancient Egyptians inspire the geometric shape of the pyramid of Cheops and I will prove that it is related to the relationship between the geometric shape of the earth and another share with the numbers of the days of the lunar year which I named relation between terrestrial pyramid and pyramid of Cheops. Afterwards I will theoretically calculate the flat surface of the poles which are equal and that the result presents the scientific proof of my hypothesis.

Key words:

Flattened Poles, lunar year earth, Cheops earth pyramid, Equatorial vertigo

Introduction :

Creation is an act of art and it reflects the excellence of the creator and his originality, it manifests itself in the creation of the planets of which I think that the measurements of these planets and the distances which separate them are well studied and well defined.

In this research I will look at the relationship between two planets that have always been a center of research for women researchers, are the earth and the moon.

I am going to put a hypothesis that shows a fundamental relationship between these two planets and that manifests itself in the relationship between the geometric shape of the earth or a circumference of it and the number of days of the lunar year.

By developing this hypothesis I will show how there was a relation between the angle opposite to the flattening of the poles and the angle opposite to the base of the terrestrial pyramid that its height presents the difference between a circumference of polar diameter and a circumference of equatorial diameter and on the other hand the relationship between the terrestrial pyramid and the pyramid of Cheops which I will reveal from where the ancient Egyptians inspired the shape and dimensions of this pyramid.

Thus, I will also show that the sum of the angles which structures the geometric shape of a circumference of the earth presents a golden ratio in relation to the degrees which makes a circle.

And finally, I will theoretically calculate the flat surface of the poles which are equal and that proving the results with measurement technology confirms the accuracy of my hypothesis.

The literature review:

First of all, the earth was declared spherical in the Greek world in the Pythagorean milieu from the 10th to the 9th century, explains Régis Morérou, teacher-researcher at the University of Paris-Diderot in the philosophy and history science laboratory. Pythagoras, a pre-Socratic Greek philosopher, would be the first to have declared that the earth was spherical.

Besides the moon exerts a tidal force on the earth, the first to have understood this cosmic mechanics is George Darien. This scientist had postulated in 1880 that the attraction of the moon deforms the earth by creating a bead which is not exactly in the direction of the moon. The attraction between this bead and our natural satellite acts as a slight brake applied to these celestial knots and dissipates some of the energy of the earth-moon system.

The rotational speed of our planet should therefore decrease. However, by virtue of the conservation of the quantity of rotational movement in the earth-moon system, if the earth slows down, the distance between it and the moon must lengthen.

These works discussed the relationship between earth-moon which manifests in the tidal force but from my point of view I think there was another relationship which manifests in the relationship between the geometric shape of a circumference of the earth and the number of lunar days.

Methodology:

First, I will determine the proportional relationship between the side of the base of the earth's pyramid and the side of the base of the Cheops pyramid that I defined by superimposing a circumference of polar diameter of the earth and a circumference of equatorial diameter of the earth.

1- Dimension of the base of the pyramid and its relation to vertigo at the equator:

We know that the number of days in the lunar year is 354.37 days. (1)

Also, one-meter equals 39.3701 inches.

To calculate the side of the base of the pyramid whose height is proportional to the difference between the polar radius and the equatorial radius.

(Vertigo at the equator).

$$354.37 \times 100 = 35437 \text{ inches}$$

$$35437 / 4 = 8859.25$$

$$8859.25 / 39.3701 = 225.024828 \text{ or } 225.025 \text{ m} = \text{side of the base of the pyramid of Khéops.}$$

$$225.025 \text{ m} \times 1000 = 225.025 \text{ km} = \text{side of the base of the earth pyramid}$$

Diagram 1: (the drawing is not to scale)

This calculation proves that the ancient Egyptians inspired the dimension of the side of the base of the Cheops pyramid from its proportional relationship to the dimension of the side of the base of the earth's pyramid which is the result of the base of the angle to be determined later and which relates to the fundamental relationship between the geometric shape of the earth and the number of days in the lunar year.

2- Resultant angles of the side of the pyramid:

In this part I will prove that the height of the pyramid of Cheops and the height of the earthly pyramid are proportional and that the ancient Egyptians chose the number of sides of the base of the pyramid relatively to this proportionality and by admitting the calculation of Nicholas Tesla.

(This drawing is not to scale)

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Tg}\alpha &= DC/AD \\ &= 112,512475 \text{ km} / 21.3846859 \text{ km} \\ \alpha &= 79,2384373393501 \\ \alpha' &= 158,4768746787 \\ AD = H &= 21,3846859 \text{ km} \end{aligned}$$

Choice of the geometric shape of the work:

- $225.025 / 1.66666666666667 = 135.0149$ soit 135.015
m = hauteur de lapyramide de Khéops
- $135.015/21.3846859 = \underline{\underline{6,3136302600544626189716445636454}}$

$$\begin{aligned} &6+3+1+3+6+3+0+2+6+0+0+5+4+4+6+2+6+1+8+9+7+1+6+4+4+5+6+3+6+4 \\ &+5+4= \\ &130=1+3+0=4 \end{aligned}$$

3- Coté de la base de la pyramide

The calculation shows that the two Heights are proportional and that the choice of number of sides is not absurd.

A

$$\sin \alpha = DC/R \text{ polaire}$$

$$\alpha = 1,01416225046284^\circ$$

$$\alpha' = 2,02832450092568^\circ$$

The angle α is the angle opposite to the half side of the base of the terrestrial pyramid and the angle α' is the angle opposite to the side of the base of the terrestrial pyramid.

4- Flat areas of the North and South Poles:

On this step I will determine the angles that structure the geometric shape of a circumference of the earth.

(This drawing is not to scale)

β'
South Pole
 $\beta = \beta' = ?$

$\mu = \mu' = 2,02832450092568^\circ$

Let C be a sphere:

$$\alpha' = \mu = \mu' = 2,02832450092568^\circ$$

$$6^\circ - (2,02832450092568^\circ \times 2) =$$

$$1.94335099814864^\circ$$

$$\beta = \beta' = 0,97167549907432$$

Reviewing the history of the circle we find that it is inspired by the geometric shape of the earth. Let's all know that the circle is made up of 360° .

I projected the number of days of the lunar year on a circumference of the earth as it is presented in the previous diagram of paragraph (3)

$$1 \text{ day} = 1^\circ$$

I subtracted the 6° (6 days) from the circumference since the lunar year is made up of 354 days.

5- The polar diameter and the equatorial diameter:

- Let's continue the search by going to prove the previous calculation and by proving that the difference between the polar diameter and the equatorial diameter is the height of the earth's pyramid.
- Polar diameter = $6356.8 \times 2 = 12713.6 \text{ km}$
- Equatorial diameter = $6378.137 \times 2 = 12756.274 \text{ km}$

Difference between the two diameters = H of the earth pyramid =
21.385 km

6- Gold percentage:

In this step we will draw attention to a percentage of gold that manifests itself in the relationship between the sum of the angles that structure the geometric shape of the earth and the degrees of a circle.

$$\frac{6 \times 100}{360^\circ} = 1.6$$

7- North pole flat surface:

To prove the hypothesis, you will theoretically calculate the flat surface of the north pole which is equal to the flat surface of the south pole and appeal to specialists to verify the theoretical results by sizing the surfaces using measurement tools. D

$$\sin \alpha = \frac{DB}{R \text{ polaire}}$$

$$DB = R \text{ polaire} \times \sin \alpha$$

$$= 6356.8 \times \sin 0.48583774953716 = 53.901638531080884549563153371184 \text{ Km}$$

= Rayon de la surface plate du pôle nord.

$$\text{Surface du pôle Nord} = \pi \times 53.901638531080884549563153371184^2$$

$$= \mathbf{9127.5413125489495797359895876218 \text{ Km}^2}$$

Conclusion :

In this research trying to prove that there was a fundamental relationship between the geometric shape of the earth and the number of days of the lunar year which followed a reasoning process that led us to prove this theoretically.

The result found proves that the approach followed in the research achieved these objectives and that it was well structured.

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